

Sodium *p*-(Mercaptoacetamido)benzenesulphonate as a Volumetric Reagent for Determination of Copper

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Sodium *p*-(mercaptoacetamido)benzenesulphonate forms an intense blackish blue, water-soluble complex with Cu^{2+} below pH 9.0. The colour changes abruptly to light yellowish green at the Cu: reagent ratio of 1:2 in the pH range 4.5 to 8.0. The iodine liberated by the action of potassium iodide on Cu^{2+} is quantitatively titrated against a standard solution of the reagent. Copper has been determined by both of these reactions in presence of a large number of foreign ions. The results have been compared with the iodometric determination of copper with sodium thiosulphate.

Sodium *p*-(mercaptoacetamido)benzenesulphonate forms an intense blackish blue, water-soluble complex with Cu^{2+} below pH 9.0. In the pH range 4.5 to 8.0, the blackish blue colour produced in the first instant changes abruptly to light yellowish green at the Cu: reagent ratio of 1:2. This marks the end point which is sharp and distinct. The reaction may be represented by equations (1) and (2), where RH stands for the reagent.

The equivalent weight of copper will therefore be equal to half of its atomic weight. The probable chelate structures of the two complexes may be represented as (I)' and (II):

The percentage purity of the reagent² is reported to be determined by titrating it against a standard solution of iodine. Authors have found that if copper solution is treated with excess of potassium iodide in the pH range 4.0 to 5.5, copper can be determined quantitatively by titrating the liberated iodine with a standard solution of the reagent, using starch

1. Emelius and Anderson, "Modern Aspects of Inorganic Chemistry", Routledge & Kegan Ltd., London, 1960, p. 239.
2. Gupta and Sogani, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, 31, 918.

as indicator (cf. thiosulphate method³). The reaction may be represented by equations (3) and (4):

In this case, the equivalent weight of copper will be equal to its atomic weight.

In the present investigation, the two types of reactions have been employed for volumetric determination of copper alone or in presence of elements which are usually associated with it. For comparison, the results of titration, as obtained by sodium thio-sulphate method, are also recorded.

EXPERIMENTAL

Approximately 5.0 g. of AnalaR copper sulphate was dissolved in one litre of water and standardised by the thiocyanate method. The solution was suitably diluted to furnish 0.02*N* copper (iodometrically).

The reagent was prepared and standardised as described by Gupta and Sogani² and its solution was prepared in oxygen-free water to provide 0.04*M* solution. Fresh solutions were employed.

About 10.0 g. of pure sodium thiosulphate was dissolved in 2 litres of distilled water containing 0.8 ml of chloroform⁴. The solution was suitably diluted to provide 0.02*N* solution and stored in a well-stoppered amber-coloured bottle.

Sodium acetate (10%, w/v), acetic acid (1%, v/v), sodium potassium tartrate (10%, w/v), sodium fluoride, (5%, w/v), ammonium thiocyanate, (20%, w/v), potassium iodide (100%, w/v), sodium carbonate (1%, w/v), NaOH (1%, w/v), and starch (0.5%, w/v) solutions were prepared in distilled water. Solutions (1%, w/v) of various foreign ions were prepared. Reagent grade chemicals were employed.

pH measurements were made with a Beckman pH meter, model H-2, and also with universal pH paper. All other apparatus was standardised.

Determination of Optimum Conditions for Titration of Cu²⁺ with the Reagent

Direct Method.—In a series of experiments, 0.02*N* copper solution (5 ml) was pipetted into a titration flask. Sodium potassium tartrate solution (1 ml) was introduced to avoid precipitation of copper. pH of the solutions was varied from 3.0. to 9.0 by adding varying amounts of NaOH, sodium acetate, and acetic acid solutions. It was then titrated against 0.04*M* reagent solution in each case. It was found that in the pH range 4.5 to 8.0, the change from intense blackish blue colour produced in the first instant, to yellowish green colour was abrupt and distinct at the Cu: reagent ratio of 1:2. The authors preferred to work in

3. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis," Longmans, London, 1951, p. 337.

4. Kassner and Kassner, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1940, 12, 656.

the lower pH range of 4.5 to 5.5 to avoid precipitation of copper as hydroxide. This pH can be maintained easily by adding about 7.0 ml of 10% sodium acetate solution to 20 to 40 ml of the reaction mixture.

Indirect Method.—A series of solutions was prepared as described above in iodine flasks and 0.2 ml of 100% potassium iodide solution was added in each case. The flasks were stoppered, shaken gently to mix the contents, kept for a minute or so, and the iodine liberated was titrated against 0.04 *M* reagent solution, using starch as indicator. Ammonium thiocyanate (1 ml) was added in each case, near the end point, and titration completed. The ratio of the reagent to copper was found to be 1:1 in the pH range of 4.0 to 5.5.

TABLE I
Volume of 0.02*N*-CuSO₄ taken = 20.0 ml.

1% Soln. of foreign ion added.			0.04 <i>M</i> Reagent solution for Procedure I.	0.02 <i>N</i> Thio soln.
Nil			20.05 ml	20.00 ml
Nil			20.00	20.05
Nil			20.00	19.95
Ca ²⁺	chloride	2.0 ml	20.05	20.00
Sr ²⁺	nitrate	2.0	20.05	20.05
Ba ²⁺	chloride	2.0	20.00	20.00
Zn ²⁺	sulphate	2.0	20.00	19.95
Ni ²⁺	"	2.0	20.05	20.00
Co ²⁺	"	2.0	20.05	20.00
Mn ²⁺	"	2.0	20.00	20.00
Mg ²⁺	"	2.0	20.00	20.00
Pb ²⁺	nitrate	2.0	20.05	20.05
Sn ²⁺	chloride	2.0	20.05	..
Fe ³⁺	sulphate	2.0	20.50	..
Al ³⁺	"	2.0	20.00	10.00
Sb ³⁺	chloride	2.0	20.05	..
Ag ⁺	nitrate	2.0	..	10.00
Cr ³⁺	chloride	0.1	20.00	10.00
ZrO ₂ ⁺	nitrate	2.0	20.05	10.05
VO ₃ ⁻¹	sodium	2.0	20.00	..
MoO ₄ ²⁻	"	2.0	20.00	10.00
NO ₂ ⁻	potassium	2.0	20.00	..
SO ₃ ²⁻	sodium	2.0	20.00	..
AsO ₃ ³⁻	"	2.0	20.05	..
PO ₄ ³⁻	"	2.0	20.00	10.00

Procedure I (Direct Titration).—A standard copper solution (20 ml of 0.02*N*; copper content should not be lower than 0.01*N* iodometrically for accurate work) was pipetted into a 250-ml conical flask and excess of acid removed by dropwise addition of sodium carbonate solution to the point of slight turbidity which was subsequently removed by dropwise addition of acetic acid solution. About 7.0 ml of sodium acetate solution was introduced to maintain the pH between 4.5 and 5.5 throughout the titration. It was then titrated with shaking with the standard solution of the reagent (0.04*M*) till blackish blue colour produced in the first instant just changed to yellowish green. The results are recorded in Table I.

Procedure II (Iodometric Titration with the Reagent).—A standard copper solution (20 ml of 0.02*N*) was pipetted into a 250-ml iodine flask and excess of mineral acid and subsequent turbidity were removed as in procedure I. A potassium iodide solution (1 ml of 100%, w/v) was introduced into it. The flask was stoppered, shaken gently to mix the contents, and kept aside for a minute or so. The stopper was washed into the flask and titrated against the standard reagent solution (0.04*M*) using starch as indicator. Ammonium thiocyanate (5 ml) was added near the end point to liberate the adsorbed iodine and the titration completed. Results are recorded in Table I.

A third titration was simultaneously carried out iodometrically with 0.02*N* sodium thiosulphate solution. The results are recorded in Table I.

Effect of Foreign Ions.—A known volume of the solution of the foreign ion was introduced before neutralisation of excess acid with sodium carbonate solution. The rest of the procedure was the same as above. In case of Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} , 10 ml of sodium fluoride solution and in case of Sb^{3+} , 5 ml of sodium potassium tartrate solution were added before neutralisation of excess of acid with sodium carbonate. Fe^{2+} must, however, be oxidised to Fe^{3+} . Ag^+ , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Au^{3+} , Pt^{4+} , and Pd^{2+} interfered in procedure I. In case of Sn^{2+} , the end point was not sharp and higher results were obtained. For making determination in presence of Pb^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , and Ca^{2+} , copper acetate solution was employed. Limiting concentrations have not been found except in the case of Cr^{3+} .

CONCLUSION

Sodium *p*-(mercaptoacetamido)benzenesulphonate is superior to the common sodium thiosulphate reagent in two respects. Firstly, nitrite, sulphite, arsonite, and other similar type of reducing agents do not interfere and secondly, the reagent can be used as a standard substance for the volumetric determination of copper as it is a stable compound in solid state.

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